

INVESTIGATE THE PROPERTIES OF SIMPLE AND COMPLEX ETHERS

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Simple ethers. The hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl group in the alcohol molecule substances formed by the substitution of a radical are called simple ethers.

Simple ethers can be the same or different depending on the structure of the radicals in the molecule. In the same ordinary ethers $R-O-R$ also, CH_3-O-CH_3 , $C_2H_5-O-C_2H_5$. Various common ethers are also called mixed common ethers. Their radicals are different.

Nomenclature and isometry. Simple ethers, usually in accordance with the rational nomenclature, that is, ether in the name of radicals the word is added, for example:

CH_3-O-CH_3 dimethyl ether, methyl ether

$C_2H_5-O-C_2H_5$ dimethyl ether, ethyl ether

$CH_3-O-C_2H_5$ methyl ethyl ether

If the radicals are the same in simple ethers, often, di- will be omitted. Simple ethers are hydrocarbons ($C_nH_{2n+1}-H$) the hydrogen atom is alkoxy ($R-O-$) group

derivation with $C_nH_{2n+1}-O-R$ is considered, when named according to the Geneva nomenclature. Therefore, simple ethers to the Geneva nomenclature the name of the hydrocarbon in the corresponding name of the alkoxy group it is added. For example:

CH_3-O-CH_3 methoxymethane

$CH_3-O-CH_2-CH_3$ methoxyethane

$CH_3-CH_2-O-CH_2-CH_3$ ethoxyethane

Simple ethers, for example, dimethyl ether in the radical CH_3-O-CH_3 A homologous series is formed when the hydrogen atom is substituted one after the other with the methyl radical:

CH_3-O-CH_3 ; $CH_3-O-CH_2-CH_3$;

$CH_3-CH_2-O-CH_2-CH_3$

The isometry of simple ethers depends on the isometry of radicals will be. Each of the simple ether isomers is a homologous series can produce That is why

ordinary ethers are called metamerism in addition to radical isometry type of isometry is also found. It consists of various radicals. Compounds that have the same molecular formula are called metameric compounds.

Physical properties. Dimethyl and methyl ethers from simple ethers is a gas under normal conditions, and the rest is a colorless liquid that moves easily. (C₁₇H₃₅) Simple ethers starting from 0 will be in a solid state. Simple ethers are lighter than water almost insoluble. It is easily soluble in organic solvents and it is also itself often dissolves organic substances. The boiling point of simple ethers is lower than that of the alcohols from which they are formed. For example, dimethyl ether boils at -23.6°C, and methyl alcohol boils at + 65°C.

Chemical properties. Simple ethers are chemically rare substances and are very difficult to hydrolyze. that is why and simple ethers are solvents in various chemical reactions is used as Concentrated sulfuric acid is suitable for simple ethers or converts to sour complex esters and alcohols complex ethers.

Complex esters. Carboxyl of carboxylic acids as complex esters compounds formed by the replacement of a hydrogen atom in the group with a radical. They are uncommon

as can be expressed. Here R and R₁ are hydrocarbon radicals, whether they are the same or different possible.

Nomenclature. Complex ethers are often relevant called by the name of acids and alcohols. For example,

Complex esters are very common in nature. It plays an important role in the life of plants and animals. They are flowers and determines the pleasant aromas of fruits. Fats that are important for life are also complex ethers.

Obtainable. Interaction of carbonic acids with alcohols complex ethers are formed. For example, a catalyst (concentrated sulfate or with the presence of hydrochloric acid) a complex ether - ethyl acetate is obtained:

OH

Physical properties. The simplest monobasic acids and alcohols complex ethers - liquids lighter than water, volatile and in most cases aromatic substances. For example, isopentyl ether of acetic acid (isopentylacetate) has a pear smell, and butyl ether of fatty acid has a pineapple smell.

The boiling and melting points of complex ethers are lower than those of the corresponding organic acids. Just a molecule only complex ethers with relatively small masses soluble in water.

Most complex ethers have a fruity aroma. For example, oil - from butyl ether - from pineapple, from isovalerian-ethyl ether - smells like apples.

Chemical properties. A characteristic property of complex ethers is their reaction with water (hydrolysis). For example:

Usage. Most complex ethers are good solvents for organic substances. They are soft drinks, used in the production of candies and other food products it is used as an additive and in perfumery. Complicated ethers, methyl acrylates

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